

COGNITIVE AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE INTERPRETER'S ACTIVITIES

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ABSTRACT

The article highlights the current problems of Cognitive and psychological features of the interpreter's activities. Also author gave more information about that. The following article provides information about the psychological changes that occur in adolescents. The author summarizes the results of his empirical research in this article.

Key words: *interpreter, person, emotional intellect, general intellect, emotional competence, empathy, frustration, personal communication, socialization, interpersonal relationships.*

Introductions

As you know, emotional intelligence is a highly developed own sense of personality- understanding emotions and feelings of other people, managing them is the ability to research it into the problem of emotional intelligence in the science of psychology it is unlikely that a number of new approaches will arise. Psychological according to the content, emotional intelligence is a lightening of the feelings of other people it is also the justification of emotions based on understanding or intellectual processes. All components of emotional consciousness in a person are inextricably linked with each other, their interdependence contributes to the effective course of interpersonal relationships gives [1]. Emotional intelligence is a rapidly developing study in modern psychology one of its areas. Many researchers have attributed this

phenomenon to tamoni. Emotional intelligence is the perception of emotions, the perception of other people and their personal the ability to realize goals, motivations and desires, as well as practical problems to solve their feelings and feelings of other people management[2]. His own feeling without managing their own, a person in his professional career and personal life does not succeed, because the successful solution of common problems perception of emotions and related. With intelligence in most emotional situations there are situations when you need to be judged. Control and control of emotions an important ability of an individual[3]. There have been many studies on this for example: A.K. Kravtsova considers issues of emotional intelligence and leadership in the team. T.I.Solodkova analysis of the resource capabilities of emotional intelligence in the work of teachers makes, K.S. Kuznetsova, I. N. Meshcheryakova and others in people of different ages they study the pressing problems of emotional intelligence. In the early 1930s L.S.Vigotsky considers both the effects themselves and the emotions to be more complex psychological systems bilsn combines the problem of studying the order and relationship of links and he defined it as the main task of scientific psychology. Emotional states and another famous Russian scientist of ideas about the unity and interdependence of intelligence A.N.It can be observed in the works of Leontev, who divided thinking from emotional activity it is impossible to see on the floor, and the most important feature of emotions noted that they are inside [4].

Methods

As early as the 1930s, psychologist Edward Thorndike described the concept of " social intelligence he had described it as the ability to get along with other people. In the 1940s psychologist David Wexler various effective components of intelligence in people's lives suggested that it could play an important role in how successful it was. John Gottman, an experienced psychologist about emotional intelligence, believed that we were right stereotypes of behavior contribute to the development of a child's

emotional intelligence (EQ) explicitly stating that he would not give, he noted the quids:

- Pay attention to the child's emotions;
- Emotional as an opportunity to learn and communicate with your child use;.from the expression
- Show empathy and better understand the child's mood;
- Help your child overcome difficult situations and problems.

Emotional intelligence, deep empathy, among other things, makes you feel to lead and follow others wisely without losing , respect the boundaries of others and develop your own love and includes the ability to accept and give support. Science emotional divides intelligence into 5 separate components. The first three are self-contained and the other two are belonging to the outside world: [5]

1. Self-confidence:
2. Self-regulation:
3. Self-stimulation:
4. Empathy:
5. Social competence.

Emotional intelligence (EQ) is the perception, interpretation, demonstration of emotions, control and effective and constructive communication with others and with the ability to use for communication. Expressing and controlling these emotions the ability is very important, but to understand, interpret and understand the feelings of others the ability to respond to them is also important. Some of the main signs and examples of emotional intelligence: [1, 3]

- Ability to identify and describe what people feel
- Knowledge of personal strengths and limitations
- Self-confidence and self-acceptance
- The ability to give up mistakes
- Acceptance and acceptance of changes ability
- Strong sense of interest, especially to other people

- Feelings of empathy and anxiety towards others
- Sensitivity to other people's feelings show
- * Acceptance of liability for errors
- Ability to control emotions in difficult situations

Results

Tom meaning according to, the concept of emotional intelligence with emotional competence are interrelated and are counted with the same content. The "emotional competence" is- in understanding and blessed by man the feelings of himself and others all knowledge and skills and qualifications. For example, besides the familiar ability the ability of a person to understand his merits and inspire others, to influence them provides the opportunity to develop. In a suitable way, it is better to make your own emoticons people capable of managing, resistant and able to work in various stress situations holder is counted. Emotional intelligence it is also the fact that we all have feelings hidden in US perhaps, let's say who was not interested in the feelings of a teenager, and he went to the universe jar lowered; I need attention, I need help, but Hecht who did not hear it and as a result, his feelings were left unanswered. The consequence is that in it emotional intelligence becomes more and more declining decided not to use his feeling for any further activity. As a result it began to turn into a biorobot, which is why in society the emotionality of intellect we all understand and realize how important it is. Zeroki, the opportunities created by our state are at the same time mental and emotional in young people you can give out Your Side achievements. And this is anew-new thoughts and gives innovation. When and in what order do we use emotional intelligence? Uni the following in a series of examples we carry out during our activities. one Work at school or at work. High emotional intelligence gives you a place to work helps overcome social complexities, guides others, and encourages and in your career, you will be encouraged. Indeed, it is important to evaluate methods when it comes to emotional intelligence, many companies now like technical ability they evaluate as important and use the EQ test before hiring. Your physical health. If

you can't control your feelings, you may also be unable to manage stress. This leads to serious health problems can lead. Uncontrolled stress increases blood pressure, makes the immune system suppresses, increases the risk of heart attack and stroke, contributes to infertility and accelerates the aging process. The first step to improving emotional intelligence is learning how to manage stress. Your mental health. Uncontrolled emotions and stress are also mental it can affect your health, making you vulnerable to anxiety and depression makes. If you can't understand your feelings, you can feel free even to build strong relationships if you can't or can't control them you fight. This, in turn, can make you feel lonely and isolated, and mental health it can exacerbate any problems associated with it.

Conclusion

In other words, today's daytime emotional intellect the concept of local in research, the need for learning is considered high, both theoretically and practically. Of course, emotional intelligence is noticeable in the implementation of social and biological needs in an individual influence; theoretical, practical and professional training in professional interests are it is from the sentence. The development and formation of this intelligence is an important factor in the individual regarded as. General of excessively high levels of behavior and activity it is seen as a false reaction that manifests itself in its disorder. High anxiety individuals belonging to the category have a wide range for their respect and vital activity situations tend to see in themselves a personal and situational threat. Such in cases, they respond to the exact state of tension. Anxiety general in the sense that the same comes to the surface through your initial experiences that appear in our memory. That is why good memories can keep a person from worrying [6]. Opening up the nature of emotional intelligence is a culture of understanding others it is natural that it serves to increase. Because mental abilities and emotional abilities are one is closely related to one. Changes in emotional experiences in the individual of course it can also cause intellectual abilities to change. Most certain emoticons by scientists increase the mental abilities of people or reduction

have been shown to have an effect. The fact that a person can control his emotions of course it has been found that is important in finding its place in society. Considering modern leader models during the training of leaders at the moment the acquisition is also carried out through emotionality intelligence, which is why how important it is for the leader to understand and motivate his employees it should be taken into account[8]. If more extensive research is carried out in this regard, then the development of emotional intelligence typologically understanding, emotional intellect and age, emotional intelligence and profession, emotional intelligence and its role in management, typological of personality emotional intelligence aspects are unlikely to find a specific solution.

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